

Thomas Hobbes' Contributions to Development Theory and Political Philosophy

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Abstract

This study critically examined Thomas Hobbes' contributions to development theory and political philosophy. The study aimed to analyze Hobbes' key ideas, including the conception of human nature, the theory of the social contract and state formation, and the perspective on sovereignty and absolute power, and to assess their lasting impact on subsequent development theories and political thought. The analysis drew on a review of Hobbes' primary works, such as *Leviathan* and *De Cive*, as well as secondary sources that examined the influence of these ideas. The study employed a qualitative, interpretive approach, situating Hobbes' theories within the broader intellectual and historical context of the Enlightenment era. The findings demonstrated that Hobbes' mechanistic view of human nature, driven by self-preservation and competition, highlighted the necessity of a structured society and a strong governing authority to mitigate societal disorder. The social contract theory, which justified the transfer of individual rights to a sovereign power in exchange for security and order, profoundly shaped theories of state formation and the legitimacy of political authority. Moreover, Hobbes' advocacy for absolute, centralized sovereignty continued to inform debates on the role of the state in ensuring stability and progress. The study concludes that Hobbes' ideas remain highly relevant in analyzing and addressing contemporary development challenges, particularly in societies grappling with issues of governance, corruption, and the breakdown of social contracts, as exemplified by the case of Nigeria. The study recommends that countries facing such challenges should prioritize strengthening their governance structures and political institutions to maintain order, enforce the rule of law, and create conditions for societal well-being and security. Hobbes' work continues to serve as a foundation for ongoing discussions on the nature of the state and the mechanisms required to promote sustainable development.

Keywords: *Development Theory, Political Philosophy, State of Nature, Social Contract, Sovereignty, Absolute Power, Governance.*

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Introduction

The development of political theory has been profoundly influenced by the contributions of key philosophers throughout history. Among these thinkers, Thomas Hobbes stands out for his seminal work on the nature of human society and governance. Hobbes's ideas, particularly as articulated in his magnum opus, *Leviathan* (Hobbes, 1651), have laid the groundwork for many modern concepts of political authority, social contract, and the nature of human behavior in the context of societal development. This

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study aims to explore Hobbes's contributions to the development of political theory, examining how his thoughts have shaped contemporary understanding of governance, human nature, and the social contract.

Development, broadly understood, refers to the process of growth, progress, and positive change in human societies. Development theories attempt to explain how and why societies evolve, addressing economic, social, political, and cultural dimensions of change. These theories have emerged from various disciplines, including economics, sociology, political science, and philosophy, each offering unique perspectives on the nature and mechanisms of societal progress (Egbo, & Ezeaku, 2020).

Development theories can be traced back to the Enlightenment era, when thinkers began to systematically analyze social and political structures. Among these early contributors, Thomas Hobbes (1588-1679) stands out as a pivotal figure whose ideas significantly shaped our understanding of social and political development. Although Hobbes predates the formal establishment of development studies as a field, his insights into human nature, social organization, and the role of government have profoundly influenced subsequent theories of societal progress and state formation.

Hobbes' seminal work, "Leviathan" (1651), emerged during a period of intense political turmoil in England. This context deeply influenced his thinking about the foundations of social order and the conditions necessary for human flourishing. Hobbes proposed a theory of social and political development that starts from a hypothetical "state of nature" and culminates in the formation of a sovereign state through a social contract (Hobbes, 1651/1996).

The aim of this study is to critically examine Thomas Hobbes' contributions to development theory and its implication in Nigeria Society, focusing on four specific areas:

1. Thomas Hobbes conception of human nature and its implications for social organization
2. Thomas Hobbes theory of the social contract and state formation
3. Thomas Hobbes theory of sovereignty and absolute power
4. The lasting impact of Thomas Hobbes ideas on subsequent development theories and political philosophy

Concepts Clarification

Development

Development refers to the process through which societies achieve improvements in economic, social, political, and cultural dimensions, leading to an enhanced quality of life for individuals. It involves structural changes that make institutions more effective, governance more transparent, and societies more equitable (Todaro & Smith, 2015).

Recent scholarship has emphasized that development should be viewed as a complex, non-linear process. For instance, Pouw and Gupta (2017) advocate for a holistic approach that considers well-being, environmental sustainability, and social inclusion alongside economic growth. In this view, Sen (1999) argued that development is not just about metrics like Gross National Product (GNP) growth or personal income increases but should focus on expanding people's real freedoms. While economic factors can contribute to these freedoms, true development involves improving broader conditions such as education, healthcare, and political rights.

Therefore, development encompasses more than economic growth; it includes advancements in health, education, political stability, and social inclusion. In exploring this broader concept, development theories address these dimensions of change. Dudley Seers, for example, defined development as a process of reducing or eliminating poverty, inequality, and unemployment (Sakalasooriya, 2020).

Similarly, Edgar Owens emphasized that true development involves human development rather than just material advancement. Thus, development is a multifaceted concept that includes transforming societies

from undesirable current states to more desirable future conditions, improving individual well-being, and achieving structural societal changes (Sakalasooriya, 2020).

Development Theories

Development theories are comprehensive conceptual frameworks designed to elucidate the processes and reasons behind societal evolution and progress. These theories emerge from a diverse range of academic disciplines, including, but not limited to, economics, sociology, political science, and philosophy (Peet & Hartwick, 2015). Consequently, they offer a multifaceted perspective on the complex phenomenon of social change.

At their core, development theories aim to unravel the intricate mechanisms that drive societal transformation. Moreover, they seek to analyze the various outcomes that result from these processes of change (Pieterse, 2010). By drawing on insights from different fields of study, these theories provide a nuanced understanding of the multidimensional nature of development.

Importantly, each discipline contributes its unique viewpoint to the discourse on development. For instance, economics might focus on the role of resource allocation and market forces, while sociology could emphasize social structures and cultural dynamics (Todaro & Smith, 2020). Similarly, political science often examines the impact of governance and power relations, whereas philosophy might explore the ethical dimensions and conceptual foundations of progress (Sen, 1999).

Furthermore, these diverse perspectives allow for a comprehensive examination of the myriad factors that influence development. These factors may include economic growth, technological advancement, institutional change, cultural shifts, and environmental considerations, among others (Potter et al., 2018). As a result, development theories offer a holistic framework for understanding the complex interplay of forces that shape societal progress.

In essence, development theories serve as invaluable tools for scholars, policymakers, and practitioners alike. They provide a structured approach to analyzing social change, forecasting future trends, and formulating strategies to promote sustainable development (Willis, 2011). Thus, these theories play a crucial role in shaping our understanding of how societies evolve and how we can work towards creating more equitable and prosperous communities.

Hobbesian Conception of Human Nature

Hobbes' political philosophy was profoundly shaped by the tumultuous period of English history in which he lived, marked by civil war and political instability. From these experiences, Hobbes derived three key lessons that underpin his political thought: the necessity of stable government, the imperative to avoid chaos, and the requirement for strong governance to prevent disorder (Lawhead, 2002).

Hobbes' approach to political theory was methodical and scientific, applying principles akin to those used in geometry and physics to understand social phenomena. His aim was not to provide a historical account of society's origins, but rather to offer a rational justification for government based on fundamental axioms about human nature (Lloyd, 2009).

Central to Hobbes' philosophy is his conception of the "state of nature," a hypothetical condition of human existence without government. In this state, Hobbes posits that all individuals are equal in their rights and capabilities, though not necessarily in physical attributes. Crucially, Hobbes argues that humans in this state are primarily driven by self-interest and the instinct for self-preservation. Contrary to Aristotle's view of humans as naturally social beings, Hobbes contends that without social conditioning, individuals lack inherent sympathy or affinity for their fellow humans. Consequently, the state of nature is characterized by perpetual fear and conflict. Hobbes famously described life in this state as "solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short" (Big-Alabo, 2019).

Hobbes' pessimistic view of human nature in the state of nature stems from his belief in psychological egoism - the idea that all human actions are ultimately motivated by self-interest. This perspective leads Hobbes to conclude that without the restraining influence of government, human interactions would be

dominated by competition, diffidence, and glory-seeking, resulting in a constant state of war (Martinich, 2005).

However, Hobbes also recognizes human rationality as a key factor in his theory. He argues that reason leads individuals to seek peace and to establish a social contract, thereby creating a sovereign power to ensure order and security (Skinner, 1996). This rational self-interest, paradoxically, becomes the foundation for social cooperation and political organization.

Hobbes' conception of human nature has had a lasting impact on political philosophy and development theory. His emphasis on self-interest as a driving force in human behavior has influenced subsequent theories of rational choice and institutional development. Moreover, his idea of the social contract as a rational solution to the problems posed by human nature has been foundational to modern theories of state formation and governance (Ishanch,2023; Big-Alabo, 2019)

Summarily, Hobbes' revolutionary approach lay in conceptualizing the state as an artificial human creation, rather than a natural or divinely ordained institution. By explaining the state of nature as a collection of self-interested individuals, Hobbes laid the groundwork for modern individualism and rational actor models in social and political theory (Moehler, 2020).

Thomas Hobbes' Social Contract Theory

In his book *Leviathan* (1651), Thomas Hobbes presents a hypothetical state of nature that precedes the establishment of a social contract. This state is governed by laws of nature, defined as “a precept or general rule, found out by reason, by which a man is forbidden to do that which is destructive to his life, or taketh away the means of preserving the same” (Hobbes, 1651, p. 69). From a mechanistic understanding of human beings and their passions, Hobbes postulates what life would be like without government—a condition he terms the state of nature. In this state, each person has a right to everything, leading to inevitable conflict, a "war of all against all," resulting in lives that are solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short.

Furthermore, within the state of nature, all men are equal in power and ability. Without a sovereign, no contract can be made without considerable doubt and suspicion. By power, Hobbes refers to the power to compel, which carries authority. Thus, without a common power to keep them in awe, there is no assurance that promises will be kept, making might the criterion of order. Hobbes' solution is to replace individual might with a leviathan that aggregates the power of all and exercises it on their behalf, ensuring that justice is maintained through fear of punishment (Oyekan, 2010).

Hobbes' social contract theory, primarily detailed in *De Cive* and *Leviathan*, emphasizes the security of individuals and the state. He presupposes that people are selfish, greedy, and aggressive in their natural state, leading to a state of perpetual war. To ensure protection, he argues that all rights should be transferred to a single sovereign entity—the State. This centralized authority, described metaphorically as a Leviathan, has the legitimate basis to judge conflicts and determine the rights and obligations of citizens. Consequently, Hobbes favors an autocratic monarchy where the sovereign's orders are beyond doubt and individuals cannot oppose the state to avoid conflicts (Liu, 2012; Zhang, 2020).

According to Sasan (2021), the rise of the social contract theory aims at achieving peace, social order, and the preservation of lives. Hobbes defines a social contract as the mutual transfer of rights to the sovereign in exchange for protection and security, forming the basis for morality and moral obligation. Life without a social contract, the state of nature, lacks a common power to instill fear and enforce rules and regulations. Therefore, the social contract establishes moral obligations and provides the framework for law and justice, promoting equality and fairness by defining right and wrong.

John Rawls, a contemporary philosopher, argues that the social contract does not need to be a historical event but serves as a justification for moral principles (Browne, 2008). For Hobbes, entering into a social contract is the only solution to the problems of the state of nature and to avoid war. This covenant requires every individual to agree not to harm one another, aiming for societal peace and order. However,

agreement alone is insufficient; a powerful sovereign is necessary to oversee society and ensure peace (Mourtiz, 2010).

Thomas Hobbes' ideas on Sovereignty and Absolute Power

Thomas Hobbes, writing in the tumultuous 17th century, developed a robust theory of sovereignty and absolute power, primarily articulated in his seminal work "Leviathan" (1651). For Hobbes, the sovereign is the ultimate source of law and authority in society, possessing absolute power to make decisions deemed necessary for maintaining peace and harmony. This sovereign, often envisioned as a monarch, has irrevocable authority that cannot be challenged by subjects (Gert, 2010).

Hobbes advocates for a sovereign with unlimited power, including the authority to reward and punish subjects according to established laws. As Hobbes (1651/1950) states, the sovereign can reward "with riches or honour" and punish with "corporal or pecuniary punishment or with ignominy every subject according to the law he has formerly made." Crucially, Hobbes insists on the indivisibility of sovereign power, arguing that it cannot be transferred without consent, forfeited, or challenged by subjects.

The functions of the sovereign, as outlined by Hobbes, are extensive. They include making judgments on doctrines, serving as the sole legislator, acting as the supreme judge in controversies, deciding matters of war and peace, appointing officials, and determining rewards and punishments. While Hobbes acknowledges three forms of commonwealth - monarchy, democracy, and aristocracy - he expresses a preference for monarchy, arguing that it can regulate power more effectively and efficiently (Sasan, 2021).

Hobbes' advocacy for absolute sovereign power is rooted in his experience of political instability and war. The Thirty Years' War (1618-1648) served as a stark illustration of the consequences of weak sovereignty, reinforcing his belief in the necessity of absolute power to maintain peace and order (Mourtiz, 2010). He contends that monarchy provides the best alignment between private and public interests, unlike other forms of government where corrupt officials might prioritize personal glory over the public good (Hood, 1964).

Despite his preference for monarchy, Hobbes maintains that people acquire the same rights under all forms of government. The difference lies not in the power itself but in the "convenience or aptitude to produce peace and security of the people" (Hobbes, 1651/1950). It's important to note that Hobbes grounds the legitimacy of sovereign power in the social contract, arguing that individuals rationally choose to transfer their natural rights to the sovereign in exchange for security and peace (Lloyd, 2009).

While advocating for absolute power, Hobbes does acknowledge certain limits to the obligation of obedience. Subjects retain the right of self-preservation and are not obliged to obey commands that would directly harm them (Sreedhar, 2010).

Summarily, Hobbes' theory of sovereignty and absolute power represents a response to the political chaos of his time, aiming to provide a framework for lasting peace and social order. While his ideas have been widely debated and often criticized, they continue to influence discussions on the nature of political authority, the balance between security and liberty, and the foundations of state legitimacy.

Thomas Hobbes' Theory and the Nigerian Moral and Democratic Society

Democracy entails the participation of the people not only in the process of choosing their representatives but also in the dialogue and legislation of the laws that govern them. In this primordial sense, democracy is truly a government of the people, by the people, and for the people (Lincoln, 2009). However, democracy as practiced in Nigeria is a perverted version of this ideal. The geographical entity known as Nigeria was created in 1914 by Lord Lugard of Britain, forcibly amalgamating the northern and southern protectorates. Despite various constitutions imposed by the British to prepare the country for democratic rule, Nigerians were not receptive, leading to a series of constitutional reviews and political chaos that delayed independence and hindered the establishment of true democracy.

Barely six years after gaining independence, was Nigeria's democratic rule interrupted by a military coup. Some scholars attribute this disruption to seeds sown by British authorities during colonial rule. Nigeria,

created from more than 250 distinct ethnic groups by the British administration, was ripe for coups and chaos (Omekara & Aja, 2022). The amalgamation of diverse ethnic and linguistic groups led to ethnic politics, which undermined the fabric of the country's political life. Nigerian politics is characterized by sleight-of-hand, dissension, division, sectionalism, and acrimony, with each tribe seeking representation in national affairs, often at the expense of merit (Omekara & Aja, 2022).

In the last 22 years of Nigeria's nascent democracy, the quality of political leadership has left much to be desired. Power, violence, and money have become instruments of statecraft in the hands of the political elite, resulting in widespread corruption and moral decay. This has led to massive insecurity, secessionist agendas, and life-threatening challenges, akin to Hobbes' state of nature where life is solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short. Nigerians face disappointments due to misgovernance, and the non-institutionalization of democracy has culminated in numerous challenges, including poverty, electoral malpractices, and lack of judicial independence (Omekara & Aja, 2022).

Hobbes' view of the state of nature, described in his book *Leviathan* (1651), aligns with the current state of Nigeria. He posited that in the state of nature, humans are in perpetual war with each other, driven by self-preservation. Hobbes argued that to escape this chaotic state, individuals must form a society and transfer their rights to a sovereign or commonwealth, which he termed the *Leviathan*. This social contract ensures order and peace, with the sovereign making and enforcing laws (Big-Alabo, 2019)

Tracing Hobbes' conception of human nature to the Nigerian context, it is evident that the country faces significant moral issues. The brutal killings by herdsmen, particularly in the Middle Belt, are linked to land disputes and reflect the government's failure to maintain peace and security. When personal security is not guaranteed, citizens revert to self-defense, leading to a state of war as described by Hobbes. The Nigerian government's inadequate response to these crises demonstrates a failure to protect its citizens, resulting in ongoing violence and moral decay (Big-Alabo, 2019)

Hobbes emphasized that without a common power to instill fear and enforce laws, society would revert to the state of nature. The Nigerian government's failure to address these moral and security issues has led to widespread disillusionment and a regression to a Hobbesian state of nature. To prevent further decline, it is imperative for Nigeria to establish strong institutions of character, ensure equitable representation, and uphold the rule of law to foster true democracy and moral integrity.

Impact of Thomas Hobbes ideas on subsequent development theories

Thomas Hobbes' political philosophy, as articulated in his seminal work *Leviathan* (1651), has had a profound and lasting impact on the field of development theory. Hobbes' core ideas about the state of nature, the social contract, and the role of the sovereign have been extensively debated, critiqued, and built upon by subsequent thinkers.

The State of Nature and the Social Contract

Hobbes' depiction of the "state of nature" as a condition of perpetual war, where life is "solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short", has been a central concept in development theory (Hobbes, 1651). He argued that to escape this bleak state, individuals rationally agree to a "social contract" that vests absolute power in a sovereign authority (Hobbes, 1651). This notion of the social contract has been highly influential, with later theorists like John Locke and Jean-Jacques Rousseau building on and critiquing Hobbes' ideas (Locke, 1689; Rousseau, 1762). Their debates over the origins of political authority and the balance between individual rights and state power have shaped the evolution of political development theory (Tuck, 2002; Strauss & Cropsey, 1987).

The Role of the State

Hobbes' advocacy for a strong, centralized state as the solution to societal chaos has been a subject of much discussion and disagreement in development studies. While some theorists have embraced Hobbes' vision of the state as necessary for ensuring security and stability, others have been critical of his defense of absolute sovereignty (Burns, 1987; Tuck, 2002). Dependency theorists, for example, have challenged Hobbes' state-centric approach, arguing that the concentration of power in the hands of the state can

actually impede development by perpetuating global inequalities (Rapley, 2007; Greig et al., 2007). Modernization theorists, on the other hand, have drawn on Hobbes' emphasis on the state's role in driving societal transformation (Cowen & Shenton, 1996; Preston, 1996).

Influence on Contemporary Thought

Hobbes' ideas continue to be debated and reinterpreted in the 21st century. His concepts of the state of nature, the social contract, and the role of the sovereign have been applied to analyze contemporary development challenges, such as the breakdown of social order, the rise of non-state actors, and the legitimacy of governing institutions (Sakalasoorya, 2020). For example, some scholars have drawn parallels between Hobbes' state of nature and the instability and violence seen in failed or fragile states, highlighting the need for strong, effective governance (Fukuyama, 2014; Rotberg, 2003). Others have explored how Hobbes' ideas can inform the design of development interventions and the construction of social contracts in the modern era (Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012; North et al., 2009). From the foregoing, Thomas Hobbes' political philosophy, particularly his concepts of the state of nature and the social contract, has had a lasting and multifaceted impact on development theory. While his ideas have been widely debated and critiqued, they continue to shape contemporary discussions on the role of the state, the origins of political authority, and the challenges of achieving sustainable development.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Thomas Hobbes' contributions to development theory and political philosophy offer crucial insights into human behavior, state formation, and the importance of strong governance structures. His theories on human nature, social contracts, sovereignty, and absolute power remain pertinent in analyzing and addressing the complexities of modern political systems and the ongoing quest for peace and order in society. His work continues to inform development theories, emphasizing the role of effective governance in achieving social stability and progress. The parallels between Hobbes' description of the state of nature and contemporary challenges in societies like Nigeria underscore the relevance of his ideas in addressing issues of governance, corruption, and social contracts. Hobbes' legacy serves as a foundation for ongoing debates about the nature of the state and the mechanisms for ensuring societal well-being and security.

Recommendations

1. Encourage critical discussions on the nature of the state, the mechanisms required for promoting societal well-being and security, and the balance between individual rights and effective governance.
2. Recognize the continued relevance of Hobbes' ideas in understanding and addressing contemporary development challenges, particularly issues of governance, corruption, and social contracts.
3. Engage in further interdisciplinary research to explore the nuances of Hobbes' influence on development theories and their practical applications in diverse global contexts, such as Nigeria.
4. Emphasize the importance of strong, centralized governance in ensuring peace and order, while also acknowledging the potential risks of absolute sovereignty.
5. Strengthen Governance Structures: Countries facing governance challenges, such as Nigeria, should strengthen their institutions and governance structures. Hobbes' emphasis on a strong, centralized authority suggests that robust institutions are essential for maintaining order and preventing societal chaos.
6. Promote the teaching of Hobbes' political philosophy in educational settings, particularly in the context of development studies and political science.

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